

2015

**Organizational Review
Recommendations Report
26 September, 2015**

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Background

The Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS) was founded in 2006/2007 and now has grown to almost 5000 members from more than 80 countries. APECS organizes a variety of international, national, and local activities. As such, APECS has developed into having grassroots national committees, an international council, and an integrative executive committee coordinating and facilitating projects. At a meeting in Trondheim, Norway (28 November – 1 December 2014), the APECS Executive Committee 2014-2015 decided that a critical review of the organization should be undertaken in order to develop a strategy for the development of the organization in the coming years. An Organizational Review is an important first step towards a Strategic Plan for APECS. This is the first time that APECS has undergone an Organizational Review.

The Executive Committee appointed an **Organizational Review Committee (ORC)** to conduct this review, consisting of both members and mentors of APECS. The contact information of ORC members can be found in **Appendix 3**.

On March 9th 2015, the ORC launched an online survey to consult APECS members, mentors, and partners, as well as the wider polar community, on the relevancy of APECS' past and present activities and its structure and ongoing projects, as well as to identify future needs of early polar career scientists and the polar community at large. After multiple virtual meetings, on April 26th 2015 the ORC met in person alongside ASSW2015 in Toyama, Japan to discuss major results and outcomes of the survey and agree on recommendations for future strategic actions listed below.

Response Statistics

The survey was structured and prepared along the lines of the terms of references developed by the APECS ExCom and included 2 pathways for respondents (active APECS members/partners/sponsors and those relatively unfamiliar with APECS). It included questions about background information, relevancy of APECS' missions and goals, current and past APECS activities and initiatives (including resources and professional opportunities), organizational structure and communications strategy, APECS partnerships, skills that are of importance to the polar community, and future visions of polar science trends that APECS should take into account for the strategic planning of its activities.

The review committee was quite pleased with the level of survey responses. Some basic summary statistics include:

- 214 total respondents from 29 countries
- Top countries: USA 22.4%; Canada 14%; UK 8.9%; Germany 8.4%; Norway 6.1%
- Gender breakdown: Female 127 (59.3%); Male 83 (38.8%); No answer 4 (1.9%)

- Age ranges: 25-29: 58 (27.1%); 30-34: 71 (33.2%); 35-39: 26 (12.1%); 40-49: 26 (12.1%); 50+: 24 (11.2%)
- Career stages of respondents are: PhD Students 63 (29.4%); Postdocs 43 (20.1%); Faculty Position 24 (11.2%); Research Scientist 22 (10.3%)
- Respondents' areas of expertise: Land 65 (30.4%); Oceans 59 (27.6%); Ice 59 (27.6%); People 26 (12.1%); Space 4 (1.9%); and Other 60 (28%)
- Member statuses: Member 153 (71.5%); Not involved in APECS 34 (15.9%); Mentor 13 (6.1%); both Members and Mentors 9 (4.2%); and Other 5 (2.3%).

See also **Appendix 5** for some informational graphs on Survey's statistics and responses.

Recommendations and Discussions

1. Overarching APECS Operational Philosophy

APECS should consider a paradigm shift in how it operates. **Everything** should have a pre-defined timeframe to be set by the ExCom/Council. Whether a committee, activity, initiative, or resource - evidence must be provided of value and sustainability throughout its lifespan – e.g., predetermined regular reporting of activities to the ExCom/Council. If an extension to lifespan is requested by the group/activity, this should be considered by the ExCom/Council. Extensions to timespan of groups/activities should be treated as an exception and not the rule.

2. Funding Status

APECS could reconsider its current funding strategy (i.e., a small, lightweight organization) because many survey respondents would value APECS as a grant-funding/ brokering organization (small research projects, conferences, etc.). This could be a source of income for APECS – organizations normally charge some percent of costs for brokering these activities.

3. Interdisciplinary Focus

Concisely put, interdisciplinary interaction between all polar research fields needs to be better stimulated within APECS.

4. Communication Strategies

- Communication among groups within APECS needs to be improved, for example science-policy, member-mentor, or northerner-visiting researcher.

- APECS is sending the right number of emails. The mailing lists and newsletters are the most important channels of communication. Continued investment in more effective use of these resources is important. For example remove/streamline discipline lists. Shift all lists to one mail server (i.e., not Mailman AND Google).
- Many members engage with APECS on Facebook. Very few do so on Twitter.
- Although respondents identified significant progress with the new website, there is still too much on the website/ it is overwhelming. It is crucial that APECS remove and/ or internally archive content!

5. APECS Membership

- Only one survey respondent was an undergraduate. APECS should work more closely with universities (and UArctic) and advisors to better establish the pipeline to APECS. This may include seeking out expertise in bridging students & politics.
- Promote and encourage young northern/ indigenous scientists.
- Think in individuals as opposed to groups to make this happen – mentor and include particular APECS members individually rather than rely on publicity.
- APECS should also consider soliciting mentors to represent different demographic groups and not just scientific disciplines.

6. Skills

- The most important skill identified was scientific writing (papers, grants, etc.). More training/workshops should focus on scientific writing of all types.
- Remove web-based technologies training. This was not seen as valuable.
- Instead of providing resources on “how to become a leader,” leadership *opportunities* suffice.
- Some additional requests included disciplinary knowledge and specific transferable skills, such as graphic design.

7. Online Resources

- Strengthen and keep up to date the polar jobs list, events calendar, and funding database. They are crucial for APECS members.

- Remove / minimize the virtual poster session, overarching polar outreach (i.e. make activities more national while keeping training international), graduate programs, and polar background information.
- APECS needs to more efficiently advertise its resources. This is an exercise in curation, not broadcasting everything all the time.
- APECS needs to stay a leader in webinars (because it is no longer a unique provider of them)! Use surveys and a data-based approach in future planning.

8. Online Activities

- No more virtual poster sessions.
- Invest in a more robust mentorship program. Capitalize on interactions. Consider an “ask a mentor” column in the Newsletter (perhaps derived from panel responses). Having a list of mentors isn’t enough to facilitate interactions, there might be a need for a contact person in between to overcome a perceived barrier. Consider some sort of dating platform approach.
- There is no need on the APECS website itself for social networking features. Other platforms will provide that and minimize the work for APECS.
- Online forums: if APECS considers re-instituting them, restrict interactive events to be centered around particular dates or events.

9. In-Person Activities

In person activities are seen as important for networking and skills development. Maintain strong work here - use surveys and a data-based approach in planning.

10. Professional Opportunities

- The selection process for reps / opportunities needs to be much more transparent than at present.
- Poster and presentation awards are not valued by the APECS members who replied to the survey, although this is likely not representative of APECS members in, for example, South American and Asian countries. Don’t invest excessive volunteer time in these unless it gains (political) capital from APECS partners.

- APECS should continue to lobby for early career opportunities/ training, but members did not see value in longitudinal assessments of career tracks.

11. Education and Outreach Activities

- E&O efforts should transcend the international and much more strongly engage national committees, although skills training should be retained.
- If APECS wants to prioritize (to remove or refocus), the least valuable activities are currently perceived to be Antarctica Day, Frostbytes, and Polar Week.

12. Partnerships

There was a strong impression that APECS partners and sponsors are quite Eurocentric. Expand geographical extent and discipline coverage by using national committees to connect to regional/local organizations/institutions.

13. APECS Leadership

53% of survey respondents have been involved in APECS leadership in some way. Many saw the APECS leadership as very open, accessible, and effective. Indeed, only 7% disagreed. However, there was still a sentiment by some that the leadership appears to be a clique sometimes or too complex to enter easily. Some recommendations to ensure a continued effective, productive APECS leadership include:

- Formalize procedures for temporary ExCom members.
- All ExCom candidates must serve a reasonable length of time on the Council (e.g., 4-6 months or Director's approval) before standing for the ExCom.
- Strong enforcement of active Council/ ExCom members. Real effort seems to be concentrated in too few people right now.
- Eliminate RAC and EOC. They do not seem currently effective.
- Renewed focus on the APECS mission statement. **Everything** APECS does should have some foundation in APECS mission and strategy.
- Always think about inviting more participation and engagement. Good people fall through the cracks too easily.
- Is an assistant director needed? Or specific project-based short term positions?

14. Future Trends in Polar Research

This section of the Survey has received the most attention from respondents with a very wide variety of suggestions. The main trends highlighted include: focusing on interdisciplinarity and multidisciplinary; strengthening collaborations and communications with indigenous communities, policy and decision-makers as well as industry representatives; focusing on public outreach and science communication; understanding the importance of science careers of different levels as well as tracking career paths; funding of science; highlighting climate change research; and many others.

To avoid exclusion of the great ideas provided, the responses were almost fully included in the report and results of the review within the **Appendix 5**. APECS has publicly quoted only those responses to which it has received the sharing permissions from respondents.

Appendix 1

Terms of Reference for Organizational Review Committee

The Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS) was founded in 2006/2007 and now has grown to almost 5000 members from more than 80 countries.

APECS organizes a variety of international, national, and local activities. As such APECS has developed into having grass -roots national committees, international council, and an integrative executive committee coordinating and facilitating projects. At the in - person meeting in Trondheim, Norway (28 November – 1 December 2014), the APECS Executive Committee 2014 - 2015 decided that a critical review of the organization should be undertaken in order to develop a strategy for the development of the organization in the coming years. An Organizational Review will be the important first step towards a Strategic Plan for APECS. This is the first time that APECS has undergone an Organizational Review.

The Executive Committee appointed an **Organizational Review Committee (ORC)** to conduct this review, consisting of both members and mentors of APECS.

The APECS Organizational Review Committee is invited to:

- Review the relevance of APECS' missions and goals to current needs of early career scientists community, partners and polar research in general.
- Study and review current and past APECS activities since its creation in 2006/2007, including but not limited to:
 - a) Evaluate the impact of current activities; which activities are of the most demand among early career scientists and should be maintained and which are of less importance
 - b) Review the current balance of acti vities (research, education and outreach, career development) for meeting APECS' mission and goals.
 - c) Identify potential areas and approaches for increased involvement in research both as collaborative projects with partner organizations and developing and implementing own research activities
 - d) Highlight major gaps in current activities and recommend changes

Review the organizational structure and its effectiveness, including the following groups and communication and interactions between them:

- a) ExCom
- b) Council
- c) Council sub - committees (RAC, MIC, EOC)
- d) National committees
- e) Working groups
- Examine the effectiveness of the relationships between APECS and other organizations for meeting APECS' goals

- Consult user community (via survey or other methods as appropriate) to evaluate the effectiveness and impact of APECS' activities
- Suggest forward --- looking strategic actions and recommendations for strengthening the organization over the next 5 years.

The ORC will have an in --- person meeting on 26 April 2015 in Toyama, Japan during the Arctic Science Summit Week 2015. An interim report should be delivered by 30 May 2015, and be put on the agenda of the APECS World Summit 2015 in Sofia, Bulgaria (6 – 8 June 2015) for discussions of the APECS leadership and National Committees. A final report is expected in fall 2015 and will be released to the APECS membership together with the APECS Annual Report. The ORC is free to request information from any committees of APECS, including the International Directorate and Executive Committee at any time. The latter should be updated on the progress of the organizational review on a regular basis.

Appendix 2

APECS Background Information

1. Mission and Goals

APECS is an international and interdisciplinary organization for undergraduate and graduate students, postdoctoral researchers, early faculty members, educators and others with interests in Polar and Alpine Regions and the wider cryosphere. Our aims are to stimulate interdisciplinary and international research collaborations, and develop effective future leaders in polar research, education and outreach. We seek to achieve these aims by:

- Facilitating international and interdisciplinary networking to share ideas and experiences and to develop new research directions and collaborations;
- Providing opportunities for professional career development; and
- Promoting education and outreach as an integral component of polar research and to stimulate future generations of polar researchers.

Details available online at <http://apecs.is/who-we-are.html>

2. Current and past activities

APECS is running numerous projects and initiatives in the field of polar research, career development, education and outreach:

Running the internet portal: **www.apecs.is**

- [Polar jobs postings](#)
- [Events postings](#) (e.g. polar-related conferences, workshops, field schools, and etc.)
- News: [APECS](#), [Partner](#) and [Polar News](#) and quarterly [Newsletter](#)
- Information on [membership](#), [mission](#), [goals](#), structure and regulative documents, publications, videos of the APECS
- [graduate programmes database](#), [funding resources database](#), [polar outreach catalogue](#), [webinar database](#),
- information on [APECS event highlights](#) and [longer-term projects](#)
- information on [education and outreach activities](#) (e.g. [International Polar Weeks](#), [Antarctica Days](#))
- other [career development information and resources](#) for early career researchers (e.g. [tips for conference](#), [polar acronyms](#))
- research related information on e.g. [polar research areas](#), [virtual poster archive](#), [academic journals](#),
- [polar outreach resources](#)

Projects, activities and programmes:

Online Career development resources and activities for polar early career researchers:

- [Research and Career Development Webinars](#)

- online workshops and conferences (e.g. [APECS Svalbard Workshop](#), [APECS Online conferences](#))
- [Virtual poster sessions](#)
- [Mentorship program](#)

Working with international partners in international polar science:

- Lobbying the interests of polar early career professionals
- Involvement of early career researchers in the activities of partner organizations
- involvement of partner organisations in activities of APECS
- Representation of the polar early career scientists community at large conferences (e.g. Arctic Frontiers, AGU, ASSW, SCAR OSC)

[In-person Events:](#)

- Career development workshops and mentor panels at conferences
- Organisation and co-organisation of international forums and summits for young researchers

Education and Outreach activities initiatives:

- organizing [International Polar Weeks](#) twice a year
- participating in [Antarctica Days](#) on 1 December
- [“FrostBytes - Soundbytes of Cools Research”](#) - Project
- leading and participating in the development of polar outreach resources (e.g. [Polar Research Book](#), [Polar Outreach Catalogue](#) as part of the IPY Education and Outreach Lessons assessment)

Conducting own research projects (e.g. the APECS Nordic [“Bridging Early Career Researchers and Indigenous Peoples in Nordic Countries”](#) project and the ICARP III - APECS-ClIC [“Where are they now project”](#)) or partnering and contributing in those in a major role (e.g. [IPY Education and Outreach Assessment](#))

Supporting the activities and project ideas of the APECS Committees and Working Groups:

- of the [Executive Committee](#) for larger new APECS initiatives and directions of the organisation
- of the [Council](#) and its committees
 - [Education and Outreach Committee](#) (Communicating polar research; Working with schools, teachers, policy-makers, general public and media)
 - [Research Activities Committee](#) (Latest technologies, methods, findings and research highlights in polar science)
 - [Membership and Involvement Committee](#) (Communication with national committees, membership engagement, mentorship programme)
- of the [APECS national committees](#)
- of [APECS Working Groups](#)

3. Organizational structure

APECS organizational structure consist of:

1) Open Council

- Members self-nominated or nominated by organizations and approved by the Executive Committee
- Contributes to the implementation of APECS activities
- Links APECS to current research activities, polar research communities, and international science groups

2) Executive Committee

- Annually elected by the open Council
- Manages the organization and approves major decisions

3) International Directorate

- The physical secretariat of APECS (currently hosted in Tromsø, Norway)
- Serves as the main point of contact and central coordinator for APECS activities, day-to-day operations, finances and institutional memory

4) National committees

- national-level organizations (relationship with the international umbrella organisation APECS regulated via Memorandums of Understanding or Letters of Agreement)

5) Working groups and Committees

- Project initiation and management (open for everyone)

4) Advisory committee

- Senior-level polar researchers and administrators
- Provides ongoing advice and support to the organisation

Schematic organizational structure of the APECS

4. Current sponsors and partners

- [APECS International Directorate](#) is sponsored by the Research Council of Norway, UiT The Arctic University of Norway, and the Norwegian Polar Institute
- Various organizations and institutes provide funding to APECS projects, initiatives and events. They include currently (in alphabetical order): Arctic Frontiers, Climate and Cryosphere (CliC) project, International Arctic Science Committee (IASC), Nordic Council of Ministers, Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research (SCAR),
- APECS is officially a partner (with and without MoU) with a number of organizations, with whom we are working together to shape the future of polar research (in alphabetical order): American Geophysical Union (AGU), Arctic Frontiers, Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP) (without MoU), Arctic Portal, Climate and Cryosphere (CliC) Project, Conservation of Arctic Flora and Fauna (CAFF), Foundation for Good Governance of International Spaces (Our Spaces) (without MoU), High North Academy (HNA), International Antarctic Institute (IAI), International Association of Cryospheric Sciences (IACS), International Arctic Science Committee (IASC), International Arctic Social Science Association (IASSA), International Glaciological Society (IGS), International Permafrost Association (IPA), Polar Educators International (PEI), Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research (SCAR), the University of Arctic (UArctic)
- APECS works together with several organizations formed to help early career scientists and professionals (in alphabetical order): ArcticNet Student Association (ASA), Permafrost Young Researcher Network (PYRN), Young Earth Scientists (YES) Network, Young Earth System Scientists (YESS)

Further information on APECS partners and sponsors can be found at <http://apecs.is/who-we-are/partners-and-sponsors.html>

Appendix 3

Organizational Review Committee Members and Contacts

<http://www.apecs.is/who-we-are/organisational-review-2015.html>

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paradigm shift, which makes working with science more unstable, more unpredictable, more temporal. They mention corruption and nepotism as more and more obvious and present. And when a highly skilled and qualified scientist with lots of awards can't find a permanent position, but has to continuously fundraise for their own salary and never know if they have a job next year, it makes me question whether I even want to pursue a scientific career. It needs to be addressed.

- Rebuild the connection to polar organisations. I have the feeling that over the last few years some of the fire has been lost. There may need to be a bit more assertive advertising needed and stronger strategic positioning of APECS to avoid the momentum being lost.
- How to maintain long-term polar projects in hostile funding climate
- involving indigenous communities
- Building the network pan-arctic, finding the ways to make the organization a must-have for early polar scientists so that all are involved and engaged because the benefit is too great to pass up.
- Communicating research to the communities!
- One of the biggest problems: The science of polar regions, and particularly the number of polar scientists, is growing very rapidly. This growth should be recognized as giving unique problems to people trying to get funding and trying to get positions... right now, the growth is sort of chaotic and without plan or conscious acknowledgement...
- The dramatic broadening of global engagement in the polar regions - reflecting the profound transformation of global geopolitics more generally. The challenges this poses for APECS is, I think, that of reaching out to a much wider international community beyond those in the OECD states that have traditionally dominated polar affairs - and even beyond the powerhouse states of the Global South. If we are to ensure global interest in the polar regions and research there, we need to penetrate the emerging educated classes in non-traditional polar areas (Africa, small island states, south and SE Asia, the Caribbean, etc)
- Helping shape funding for early career researchers, funding cuts are making competition fierce with many 'late' early career researchers competing against established senior researchers for funding. Anything to help with writing research grant proposals or use the organisation to defend retaining early-career funding segments in polar research areas would be a good future plan.
- We have less funds and need to do more. APECS network could be used to facilitate that.

- Generating funds for polar early career researchers
- promotion of more interdisciplinary high profile research
- Working with local communities on research and monitoring.
- Shift away from large funding opportunities of IPY... and therefore how to stay involved in Arctic research despite less resources available. Alternative careers and opportunities.
- Helping polar scientists find ways to connect research and science to action, including not only outreach, but also advocacy and policy. The cryosphere is undergoing rapid change and as a community we have to figure out how to use our voices to address the grand challenges. We can no longer stand by as "objective observers" but have a responsibility to engage. Few polar science career tracks tolerate "activism" but we need to figure out how to extend beyond the comfort zone of our research. I see APECS as being a community of passionate people with creative ideas and approaches that can help build the skills to let members navigate these new roles as professional scientists connected to the deeply personal passions for the polar regions.
- More collaboration between sectors (academia, business, civil society, government). Young Polar scientists and professionals will move between sectors and work between sectors.
- Grant for students
- Outreach and community involvement is growing fast. APECS needs to extend its network to include northern residents as significant contributors to the outreach and communication programs.
- Climate change and its impacts on the environment and humans, way of life. How can we, as a community, reach out in a meaningful way to the general public? Also, more digital media, videos, interactive tools.
- Keep all the current and great projects, with a higher priority on E&O - e.g. in organising a really international polar week, with communication between schools and scientists from different countries, whereas actually we have Polar Weeks in different countries, but not so much work between different countries. But all the organisation behind that is a big effort - it could be interesting to find sufficient funds to finance half a position to organize it!
- With impacts of climate change evolving, Polar science is likely to become more and more important. APECS should make sure that it strengthens its position in the Polar community.
- Doing well -- open opportunities for more helpers to participate. Even those who must be employed in other fields to fund their flexibility to participate. People in this part of the Arctic feel more like bystanders than participants in what is happening in the Arctic area.

- To continue to be present and active
- Continue to promote young scientists involvement in ongoing polar activities.
- Data management.
- We are more and more researchers on all arctic topics and concurrence will be always stronger. After the postdoc positions, the opportunities are very much reduced. Early career need more research assistant or scientific collaborator positions in all instances. Continue to group people, share experiences, tips, events is already a very good achievement that has to continue.
- take humanities more into account, its often brushed aside by overemphasis on natural sciences
- One thing that seems to be missing from many components of APECS is involvement of local/indigenous people. I highly recommend making a bigger effort to work with those populations in the future.
- Funding is evolving towards demonstrating relevance to national economies. Since national economic interests are very different by nature, APECS will have to re-define a narrative that takes that dimension into account
- I think APECS needs to be prepared for increasingly rapid environmental and social change in the Arctic, as well as increasing prominence of the Arctic that will put further demands on the APECS community (good and bad).
- training future leaders
- Outreach and education for youngs in northern communities, make bridge between young scientists and young inuit for example.
- I think APECS should really focus on developing a voice in the broader political community in some way. Its time for more scientists to have a voice at capital hill and APECS could be a great voice for early career researchers!
- Funding opportunities!
- I think APECS should push for better conditions for early career scientists overall. There is a general trend of poor working conditions, little job security, high stress levels and very unclear career paths. Why not push for more transparent funding opportunities and longer funding periods (e.g. 5 years instead of the more common 2 or 3 years)? Also, nurture logistics collaborations to make fieldwork easier for researchers just starting to plan their own projects.
- limited job opportunities on the past-postdoc level, too competitive environment. As a young researcher, is it possible to stay in my job?

- With initiatives around the "third pole", Arctic and alpine research may form stronger links in the future, China could get a more powerful player, with its very different approach to research and career development... I don't know what the highest priority should be.
- Need to ensure continuity of funding at national /international level in times of austerity
- I think it would be great for APECS to have more connections and involvements with young people (and elders) from northern and indigenous communities, since I think community-based research and the involvement of community stakeholders in the Arctic is extremely important for the future of Arctic research.
- The main trends are the Global Climate Change, such as pollution and poor conservation of nature in other continents affect the Poles and how it will manifest globally
- promoting the young researchers
- Climate Change and Sustainable Communities
- There seems to be an ever-increasing number of early career female polar researchers; that is certainly the case at my institution. Support (advice and advocacy) for women who want to remain active in research while having a family needs to be a priority, especially for women who aspire to higher levels of academic leadership - at my institution (for example), these positions are male-dominated. I realize that the topic of parental leave is handled differently by different countries (and even institutions), but I feel there needs to be more acceptance and promotion of female researchers who ALSO have a family. In my personal experience, I have heard of several professors who have discouraged their female RA's from having families, and in one instance, a woman was not hired for a position because the PI didn't want to chance having to replace her if she decided to have a family. Job security and opportunities for advancement should not be affected by the presence or absence of a uterus. The next generations of researchers need to ensure that these views change, and promote action.
- With the end of IPY, maintaining the momentum and funding for the organization will be a challenge. I think we are doing great right now, but we need to make sure this will still be the case in 5-10 years. The continued support of well-established international organizations such as SCAR and IASC will be absolutely critical here. - There will be more and more pressure from shipping and other resource development to use the Arctic. I think APECS should be more proactive at getting involved with industry to establish dialogues etc. This could create opportunities for members, and will help us all to become more effective and informed leaders in the future. - Indigenous communities are becoming increasingly efficient at advocating for

the inclusion of traditional knowledge along with science in polar research. Early-career researchers are especially receptive to such a vision, and already massively participate in TK-based research. Increasing partnerships with indigenous organizations and continue to create material and opportunities for members to develop skills in that area of research should be a priority.

- Focus on networking opportunities for early careers scientists (ECS) so that we can meet each other. Provide an ECS seat on major polar committees and working groups. Make APECS a truly international organization with functioning activities in the important Arctic and Antarctic countries.
- Decreased funding for polar research. Decreased academic job opportunities for polar researchers.
- I believe inclusion in programme steering group meeting are beneficial, and should continue.
- Involvement early career researchers in polar policy making
- The applied aspect and the impact to society will be crucial in the future; especially to get projects funded.
- Making sure more ECS come and are involved into APECS structure. Getting ECS involvement into policy making.
- non-academic or research careers... there is more to life than just those jobs and the more APECS can showcase that it's not a failure to leave research
- Polar outreach, funding opportunities, jobs and career plans.
- Intensifying interests in arctic natural resources.
- Science is being beaten down by extreme conservative groups. This will hurt society, industry, future scientific communities, students, almost every free-thinking group. Our young people need to help expand the reach of science to off-set heavily funded conservative groups who strive to limit scientific literacy.
- Developing a strong cohort of polar scientists that can work together across disciplines both in research but also in communication, to help bridge the enormous gap we face between public digestion of science, and what the research actually entails or reveals.
- Education, interdisciplinary research
- A loss of sea ice around the north pole. This should be used to demonstrate climate change and the urgency and requirement to study the polar regions and look after the environment

- Gender Balance Lack of scientific funding and reduction in early career opportunities (i.e. PhD to Post Doc)
- Perhaps branch out from strictly the polar regions? Advocating for science funding and training for how to do that. Providing more resources for students who want to study outside their country and don't know how to go about finding opportunities in other ones.
- making contacts and having dialogue with the authorities on the highest possible level.
- climate change and changes in the ecology
- Inspiring each other for multidisciplinary cooperation and long term commitments
- Climate change, interdisciplinary, conservation management, connections between poles and other latitudes (sub-arctic, sub-antarctic), exploitation of resources in polar environments
- More involvement in Social Sciences - reaching policy makers
- As funding is becoming scarce, the field is going to become more competitive so I think advice will be necessary for people wanting to stay in academic fields, such as how to boost your cv, networking advice etc. Additional emphasis on career paths outside of academia might also be appropriate.
- Education and Outreach
- The last IPY was a tremendous momentum for scientists working in polar area. Priority should be given to the best part of sciences in polar areas and avoiding too many overlapping between old programs implemented by different countries as routine.
- Russia and the other Arctic actors — relations between these
- The reduction in government research funding and full-time university faculty positions. Up-and-coming polar researchers will need to know how to make their work meaningful without as much institutional support.
- More and more interdisciplinary work. Such work is not easy, and the idea of interdisciplinary collaboration is often glossed over. I think that helping to create a culture of interdisciplinary respect is one key thing that APECS can help with.
- Climate change and its effects on human health; nutritional transition.
- Scientists and policy-makers across the polar regions must collaborate more and more as the climate changes and so communication should be emphasized.
- Involve the social sciences! Research in law, international relations, political science, etc. dedicated to the Arctic needs to work together with the pure and applied sciences if we really

want to do something for the Arctic and Antarctic. Political and legal issues do not only concern politicians, business people and lawyers. I believe in interdisciplinarity.

- APECS leadership needs to better communicate with its members what it is actually doing in order to keep the growing membership engaged and active at organising events/opportunities throughout the world. Funding will no doubt become more scarce so promoting online events will be key.
- There is a growing interest in interdisciplinary research experience. The highest priority will probably be to attain a status with the Arctic Council, and be present in as many big networking meetings as possible. The framework for ECRs is there, so we need to be more present as a resource and platform for projects (especially for international recommendations).
- I would like to see opportunities to open for scientists who do not work for national programs and more open sharing of samples to maximise information gain for the public
- Develop activities in collaboration with academy (universities and academic institutions) and create meetings to early career scientists to discuss future priorities of polar science.
- We need to make sure we have more of an influence on policies made.
- Have mechanisms that will make APECS a key organization. For example, grab the best technology applied to science to help early career scientists (and mentors, and all scientific community)... Internet ways to communicate the latest paper, the latest conference, a new app to allow access to good information...
- Scientific integrity and communicating scientific ideas to the public and the press.
- Most graduate students studying polar related topics intend to have a career in academia. There are more and more students in these fields, so the competition for academic positions is getting fiercer and most of us will have to find another kind of career. APECS should partly focus on the other opportunities we have, in particular in the private sector.
- Environmental policy and planning.

Appendix 5 Informational Graphs on Survey Results

*Please note that “EC” in the graphs refers to “Early Career Scientists”

1. APECS Missions and Goals

Do you think that APECS fulfills its missions and goals?

Yes	161	92%
No	14	8%

How important do you believe the following priorities are in polar research?

APECS Mission Importance (independent)

2. APECS Initiatives

How valuable are the following organization-level activities to the polar community?

3. Communication Skills

As a member of the polar community, how valuable are the following communication skills to you?

4. Education and Outreach Opportunities

How valuable do you believe the following education and outreach opportunities are to polar researchers?

5. Information about Research Careers

In the polar community, how important is it to provide non-scientific skills (like i.e. communication skills, teamwork, leadership, networking, time management, organization, interdisciplinary knowledge, etc.) for the following career tracks?

6. Online resources

How valuable do you believe the following online resources are to polar researchers?

7. APECS in-person activities

How valuable do you believe the following in-person activities are to polar researchers?

8. APECS Online activities

How valuable do you believe the following web-based activities are to polar researchers?

9. Professional Opportunities

How valuable do you believe the following opportunities are to polar researchers?

10. Skills

As a member of the polar community, how valuable are the following skills to you?

11. APECS Communication

Where do you usually get APECS announcements and news?

Communications

APECS communications are...

Too frequent.	14	8%
Just about right.	146	83.4%
Not frequent enough.	15	8.6%

Appendix 6 APECS Review Survey

The Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS) started as part of the International Polar Year (IPY) efforts to involve early career researchers in international polar science. As we continue to grow, we want to make sure that we are meeting the needs of our members. For more background on APECS, see this further [information online](#).

So it is time for APECS to do some self reflection. We want to find out what the polar community values and how APECS can continue to be a positive and productive force. If you haven't been involved in APECS, we very much value your impartial opinion. If you have been involved in APECS, we want to understand what you use on our website, if you attend workshops, seminars and the other activities we organize together, and how these have benefited you.

This survey should take ~15 minutes to complete. Please be honest and complete with your answers as the APECS leadership will use these results to help shape how we can better address the needs of polar early career researchers. All survey results will remain anonymous and confidential, and they will only be used by APECS for this self-evaluation process. Thank you for taking the time to complete this survey as it will help us shape the future of APECS.

Let's get started...

* Required

1. General Information about you

1. **What country do you live/work in? ***

1. **What country are you originally from? ***

1. **What is your gender? ***

Mark only one answer.

- Female
- Male
-
- Prefer not to answer

1. **What is your current role / position? ***

Mark only one answer.

- Undergraduate Student

- Masters Student
- PhD Student
- Postdoc
- Research Assistant
- Research Scientist
- Faculty Position
- Looking for / in-between jobs
- Volunteer / Intern
- Other: _____

1. **What age are you? ***

Mark only one answer.

- Under 20
- 20-24
- 25-29
- 30-34
- 35-39
- 40-49
- 50+

1. **What is your general area of expertise? ***

Check all that apply.

- Atmosphere
- Ice
- Land
- Oceans
- People
- Space
- Other: _____

1. **Do APECS have your permission to anonymously quote your open-ended responses in our survey reports? ***

Mark only one answer.

- Yes, APECS may use my comments.
- No, APECS may not use my comments.

2. APECS' Mission & Goals

1. **How important do you believe the following priority is in polar research:
Stimulating interdisciplinary and international research collaborations? ***

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Important</i>						<i>Very Important</i>

1. **How important do you believe the following priority is in polar research:
Developing effective future leaders in polar research? ***

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Important</i>						<i>Very Important</i>

1. **How important do you believe the following priority is in polar research:
Developing effective future leaders in polar education and outreach? ***

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Important</i>						<i>Very Important</i>

1. **What other priorities need to be addressed to maintain continuity in polar research into the future?**

1. **Please rank the mission objectives from least important (1) to most important (3):**

*

*Mark only one * per row.*

	1	2	3
Stimulating International and Interdisciplinary Research Collaborations			
Developing leaders in polar research			

Developing leaders in polar education and outreach			
--	--	--	--

3. Skills

As a member of the polar community, how valuable are the following skills to you?

1. **Networking** *

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Communication** *

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Interdisciplinary Knowledge** *

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Leadership** *

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Team Management** *

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
--	----------	----------	----------	----------	----------	--

<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>
---------------------	--	--	--	--	--	----------------------

1. **Time Management** *

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Logistics / Organization** *

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Web-based technologies (e.g. webpages, online conferencing, etc.)** *

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Other?** _____

1. **Please rank the skills above from least valuable (1) to most valuable (8):** *

*Mark only one * per row.*

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
--	----------	----------	----------	----------	----------	----------	----------	----------

<i>Networking</i>								
<i>Communication</i>								
<i>Interdisciplinary Knowledge</i>								
<i>Leadership</i>								
<i>Team Management</i>								
<i>Time Management</i>								
<i>Logistics / Organization</i>								
<i>Web-Based Technology</i>								

4. Communication Skills

As a member of the polar community, how valuable are the following communication skills to you?

1. Oral Communication (popular) *

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. Oral Communication (scientific) *

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. Written Communication (popular) *

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
--	----------	----------	----------	----------	----------	--

<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>
---------------------	--	--	--	--	--	----------------------

1. Written Communication (scientific) *

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. Please rank the communication skills above from least valuable (1) to most valuable (4): *

*Mark only one * per row.*

	1	2	3	4
<i>Oral Communication (popular)</i>				
<i>Oral Communication (scientific)</i>				
<i>Written Communication (popular)</i>				
<i>Written Communication (scientific)</i>				

5. Career Tracks

In the polar community, how important is it to provide non-scientific skills (like those mentioned previously. i.e. communication skills, teamwork, leadership, networking, time management, organization, interdisciplinary knowledge, etc.) for the following career tracks?

1. Full-time polar researcher *

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
--	----------	----------	----------	----------	----------	--

<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>
---------------------	--	--	--	--	--	----------------------

1. **Teaching & research appointment at University level ***

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Academic Administration ***

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Research support staff ***

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Education & outreach specialist ***

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Science/Research Coordinator ***

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Polar Policy Maker ***

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
--	----------	----------	----------	----------	----------	--

<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>
---------------------	--	--	--	--	--	----------------------

1. **Non-polar careers ***

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Other career tracks?** _____

1. **How important is it to provide information about and access to non-academic career tracks?**

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Important</i>						<i>Very Important</i>

6. Online Resources

How valuable do you believe the following online resources are to polar researchers?

1. **Polar Jobs Postings ***

<http://www.apecs.is/career-resources/job-board.html>

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Events postings (e.g. polar-related conferences, workshops, field schools, and etc.) ***

<http://www.apecs.is/events.html>

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Polar Newsletter ***

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Graduate programmes database ***

<http://www.apecs.is/career-resources/graduate-programmes.html>

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Funding resources database ***

<http://www.apecs.is/career-resources/funding-resources.html>

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Polar outreach catalogue ***

<http://www.apecs.is/outreach/polar-outreach-resources/polar-outreach-catalogue.html>

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Information about APECS and its ongoing projects ***

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Tips for conference attendance ***

<http://www.apecs.is/career-resources/tips-for-conferences.html>

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
--	---	---	---	---	---	--

<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>
---------------------	--	--	--	--	--	----------------------

1. **Polar acronyms ***

<http://www.apecs.is/research/who-s-who.html>

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Background information on polar research areas ***

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Virtual poster database ***

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Background on academic journals ***

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Polar outreach resources ***

<http://www.apecs.is/outreach/polar-outreach-resources.html>

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **What other online resources would be valuable to polar researchers?**

7. Web-Based Activities

How valuable do you believe the following web-based activities are to polar researchers?

1. **Research-related Webinars ***

<http://www.apecs.is/career-resources/apecs-webinars.html>

Mark only one answer with *

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Career Development Webinars ***

<http://www.apecs.is/career-resources/apecs-webinars.html>

Mark only one answer with *

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Online workshops and conferences ***

Mark only one answer with *

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Virtual poster presentations ***

<http://www.apecs.is/research/virtual-posters/virtual-poster-session-2010-2012.html>

Mark only one answer with *

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Mentorship program ***

<http://www.apecs.is/career-resources/mentor-database.html>

Mark only one answer with *

	1	2	3	4	5	
--	---	---	---	---	---	--

<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>
---------------------	--	--	--	--	--	----------------------

1. **What other web-based activities would be valuable to polar researchers?**

1. **Please rank the web-based activities above from least valuable (1) to most valuable (5): ***

*Mark only one * per row.*

	1	2	3	4	5
<i>Research-Related Webinars</i>					
<i>Career Development Webinars</i>					
<i>Online Workshops and Conferences</i>					
<i>Virtual Poster Presentations</i>					
<i>Mentorship Program</i>					

8. In-person Activities

How valuable do you believe the following in-person activities are to polar researchers?

1. **Career development workshops at conferences ***

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Mentor panels at conferences ***

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	

<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>
---------------------	--	--	--	--	--	----------------------

1. **Organisation of international forums and summits for young researchers ***

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **What other in-person activities would be valuable to polar researchers?**

1. **Please rank the in-person activities above from least valuable (1) to most valuable (3): ***

*Mark only one * per row.*

	1	2	3
<i>Career development workshops</i>			
<i>Mentor panels</i>			
<i>Forms and summits for young researchers</i>			

9. Professional Opportunities

How valuable do you believe the following opportunities are to polar researchers?

1. **Financial support to attend conferences and workshops ***

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Early career positions on conference organizing committees ***

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
--	----------	----------	----------	----------	----------	--

<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>
---------------------	--	--	--	--	--	----------------------

1. **Early career positions as conference session co-conveners ***

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Early career positions on international science planning / evaluation committees ***

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Early career poster and oral presentation awards at conferences ***

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Active engagement in international science groups (e.g. within SCAR/IASC groups) ***

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **What other opportunities would be valuable to polar researchers?**

1. **Please rank the professional opportunities above from least valuable (1) to most valuable (6): ***

*Mark only one * per row.*

	1	2	3	4	5	6
--	----------	----------	----------	----------	----------	----------

<i>Financial Support</i>						
<i>Positions on organizing committees</i>						
<i>Session Co-Conveners</i>						
<i>Positions on planning / evaluation committees</i>						
<i>Conference Awards</i>						
<i>Active engagement in international groups</i>						

10. Education & Outreach Opportunities

How valuable do you believe the following education and outreach opportunities are to polar researchers?

- Organizing International Polar Weeks twice a year ***

<http://www.apecs.is/outreach/international-polar-week.html>

Mark only one answer with *

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

- Participating in Antarctica Day on 1 December ***

<http://www.apecs.is/outreach/antarctica-day.html>

Mark only one answer with *

	1	2	3	4	5	
--	----------	----------	----------	----------	----------	--

<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>
---------------------	--	--	--	--	--	----------------------

1. **“FrostBytes - Soundbytes of Cools Research” Project ***

<http://www.apecs.is/outreach/frostbytes.html>

Mark only one answer with *

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Connections to local classrooms and outreach events ***

Mark only one answer with *

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Leading and participating in the development of polar outreach resources (e.g. Polar Research Book, Polar Outreach Catalogue as part of the IPY Education and Outreach Lessons assessment) ***

<http://www.apecs.is/outreach/polar-outreach-resources/polar-resource-book.html>

<http://www.apecs.is/outreach/polar-outreach-resources/polar-outreach-catalogue.html>

Mark only one answer with *

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **What other education and outreach opportunities would be valuable to polar researchers?**

1. **Please rank the education and outreach opportunities above from least valuable (1) to most valuable (5): ***

Mark only one * per row.

	1	2	3	4	5
--	----------	----------	----------	----------	----------

<i>International Polar Weeks</i>					
<i>Antarctica Day</i>					
<i>FrostBytes</i>					
<i>Classroom and local events</i>					
<i>Polar outreach resource development</i>					

11. APECS Initiatives

How valuable are the following organization-level activities to the polar community?

1. **Lobbying for the the interests of polar early career professionals ***

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Initiating projects linking researchers and indigenous/local peoples ***

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Assessing the career tracks of polar professionals ***

*Mark only one answer with **

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Contributing an early career perspective to community initiatives/assessments ***

Mark only one answer with *

	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>Not Valuable</i>						<i>Very Valuable</i>

1. **Please rank the APECS initiatives above from least valuable (1) to most valuable (4): ***

Mark only one * per row.

	1	2	3	4
<i>Lobbying for polar early career researchers</i>				
<i>Researcher-Indigenous/local peoples projects</i>				
<i>Assessing career tracks</i>				
<i>Contributing an early career perspective</i>				

12. Member Status

1. **Are you... ***

Mark only one answer

- an APECS Member (*Skip to question 87*)
- an APECS Mentor (*Skip to question 87*)
- have been both an APECS Member & Mentor (*Skip to question 87*)
- a member of the Polar community (not involved with APECS) (*Continue to Q85*)
- Other: _____ (*Continue to question 85*)

13. Partnerships & Trends - Polar Community

1. **APECS aims to achieve mutual benefit and involvement with partnering organizations. APECS currently works with many partner organizations (see help text). What (other) organizations should APECS be working with?**
<http://www.apecs.is/who-we-are/partners-and-sponsors.html>
-
-

1. **What trends are happening in the polar community which APECS will need to account for in the next 5-10 years? What should be given highest priority in the APECS work plan for the next 5/10 years?**
-
-

(Skip to question 105)

14. Organizational Structure & Communication - Members & Mentors

1. **Which APECS groups have you been involved in? ***

Check all that apply.

- APECS Council
- APECS Working Groups
- APECS Executive Committee
- APECS Advisory Committee
- Member of APECS Membership and Involvement Committee
- Member of APECS Research Activities Committee
- Member of APECS Education and Outreach Committee
- Member of one of APECS National Committees
- I have not been active in APECS leadership.

1. **Do you think that current APECS structure is effective/efficient/inclusive? ***

Mark only one answer

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

1. **Why did you choose your answer to the previous question? ***
-

1. **Where do you usually get APECS announcements and news? ***

Check all that apply.

- APECS Newsletter
- APECS main mailing list
- APECS discipline mailing lists
- APECS national mailing lists
- General community mailing lists (e.g. Cryolist, ArcticInfo, etc.)
- APECS website
- APECS profile on Facebook
- APECS Twitter account

1. **APECS communications are...** *

Mark only one answer

- Too frequent.
- Just about right.
- Not frequent enough.

1. **How can APECS better communicate with its members?**

Please suggest any structural or communication changes that APECS should consider for further development.

15. Partnerships - Members and Mentors

APECS aims to achieve mutual benefit and involvement with partnering organizations. APECS currently works with many partner organizations: <http://www.apecs.is/who-we-are/partners-and-sponsors.html>

1. **What organizations, groups or institutes have you become familiar with through your involvement in APECS?**

For a list of APECS partners, see: <http://www.apecs.is/who-we-are/partners-and-sponsors.html>

1. **How have you specifically benefited from APECS partnerships and collaborations?**

1. **Which prominent APECS partnerships have NOT been of benefit to you?**

APECS wants to prioritize its activities. If there are partnerships you think APECS should give up,

this

is what we want to know.

1. **What (other) organizations should APECS be working with?**

16. Member & Mentor Involvement

1. **Have you been involved in any APECS online activities? ***

Mark only one answer

- Yes
- No

1. **Have you been involved in any APECS in-person activities? ***

Mark only one answer

- Yes
- No

•

1. **Have you benefited from funding via APECS? ***

Mark only one answer

- Yes
- No
- I have only been an APECS Mentor

1. **APECS runs numerous projects and initiatives in the field of polar research, career development, education and outreach. How have APECS activities helped you in your career, if any?**

1. **Do you think that APECS fulfills its missions and goals? ***

Mark only one answer

- Yes
- No

1. If no, why not?
-

17. Recommendations - Members and Mentors

1. What do you find the most useful about APECS as an organization? *

1. What aspects of APECS do you find least useful? *

18. Last Question!

1. Is there anything else that you would like to share that has not yet been addressed in this survey? Please feel free to share!

You have successfully completed the survey!

THANK YOU!

Your input is very valuable for us!